

Automated Orchestration of O-RAN Near-RT RIC with Integrated Remote xApp Management

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Abstract—The Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) architecture introduces the Near-Real Time RAN Intelligent Controller (Near-RT RIC) to enable AI-driven closed-loop control through deployable xApps. Current open-source implementations of the Near-RT RIC and xApp management are difficult to deploy and handle due to a complex Kubernetes-based installation process, configuration workflows, and the need for low-level knowledge to understand xApp operation. This demonstration addresses these challenges by proposing a purpose-built blueprint for cloud-native, automated, and portable deployment of the O-RAN Software Community (OSC) Near-RT RIC. Additionally, we introduce a remote xApp management application programming interface (API) to the support dynamic lifecycle management of xApps without requiring access to the underlying cluster. Together, these capabilities reduce deployment overhead, improve resource efficiency, and simplify experimentation with Near-RT closed-loop RAN control.

Index Terms—B5G/6G, O-RAN, Management and Orchestration, Near-RT RIC, xApp, OSC

I. INTRODUCTION

The Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) Alliance is driving a transformation of RAN architecture based on openness, programmability, multi-vendor operability, and embedded intelligence, relying on cloud-native principles, open interfaces, and the disaggregation of network entities. Within this architecture, the Near-Real Time RAN Intelligent Controller (Near-RT RIC) plays a central role by hosting xApps, which implement Artificial Intelligence (AI)-enabled or policy-driven RAN control logic operating at timescales below 1 second. Using the defined E2 interface, xApps can receive RAN Key Performance Measurements (KPMs) and issue control actions, enabling closed-loop optimization for mobility management, load balancing, or energy efficiency [1].

However, deploying and managing the Near-RT RIC component is complex in practice. Although the O-RAN Software Community (OSC) provides a reference implementation [2], its installation requires advanced Kubernetes expertise and intricate configuration. Additionally, xApp lifecycle management requires direct platform access and detailed knowledge of

E2 procedures and the various components of the Near-RT RIC platform. These factors hinder agile and portable deployments for experimentation in multi-site testbeds emulating different locations of available points of presence (PoPs), such as edge, regional, and central, replicating environments close to real setups where flexibility and dynamicity are essential, as envisioned in O-RAN specifications [3].

This demonstration addresses the above challenges by using our custom management and orchestration (MANO) framework [4] to manage a purpose-built blueprint that automates the cloud-native deployment of the OSC Near-RT RIC on any available PoP. This enables rapid multi-site deployment and repeatable experimentation, while avoiding the complexity of the current installation process. Additionally, we introduce a remote xApp management application programming interface (API) that supports the dynamic onboarding, activation, and termination of xApps without exposing the underlying Kubernetes cluster running in the PoP where the OSC Near-RT RIC is deployed. This API further improves computing resource efficiency by supporting *short-lived* xApps that perform punctual actions, eliminating the need for continuous operation. Together, these contributions enable more flexible management and orchestration of O-RAN components (i.e., Near-RT RIC and xApps) compared to other similar approaches based on FlexRIC Near-RT open-source software [5]. The defined blueprint is built as a Helm chart packaged within an ETSI NFV Network Service (NS) package, allowing seamless integration into the MANO framework. This significantly lowers the operational barrier for deploying Near-RT RIC instances and developing or testing xApps, thereby accelerating research on Near-RT closed-loop RAN control.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig. 1 shows the experimental setup deployed in the EXTREME® xG Testbed at CTTC (Castelldefels, Spain). This setup is distributed across four commercial off-the-shelf servers. One server runs our MANO platform, powered by an instance of ETSI Open Source MANO (OSM). Three servers act as PoPs, each running a single-node Kubernetes cluster. This setup represents the different locations managed by Mobile Network Operators (MNOs): central, regional, and edge cloud PoPs, where mobile entities can be distributed according to the O-RAN scenarios defined in [3]. The RAN

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Fig. 1. System Architecture under demonstration.

equipment is connected to the edge cloud, where the Falcon RX/G O-RAN switch and Precision Time Protocol (PTP) grandmaster provide synchronization between the edge cloud site and the Radio Unit (RU) LITEON FlexFi FF-RF1078I4. Two smartphones (Realme 9 and OnePlus 8 Pro), accessed via a remote desktop tool (e.g., AnyDesk), are used to generate traffic. This demonstration showcases the ability of the proposed setup to automatically instantiate a cloud-native OSC Near-RT RIC system, enhanced with a custom API server that enables the remote execution of xApps interacting with registered E2 nodes, namely the Distributed Unit (DU) and the Centralized Unit (CU).

Taking as a reference the work in [6], we have developed a Helm chart blueprint to further automate the deployment capabilities of the OSC Near-RT RIC while significantly improving its portability. Different instances of the Near-RT RIC can be created in any PoP without requiring shell access to the servers, as is currently required by [6] and the original OSC Near-RT RIC [2] software. During the design of this configuration blueprint, several enhancements were introduced compared to [6]. First, we included a system to dynamically configure and manage the communication ports between Near-RT RIC pods and running xApps to automate the simultaneous execution of the same and different xApp instances. Second, the blueprint introduces deployment-time adaptations to the original code implementation in [6] to fit the target Kubernetes environment (e.g., network configuration) where it is executed. Third, the pod responsible for executing the xApps, referred to as the *xApp executor pod*, is equipped with a Python-based REST API and a sidecar database container to enable remote xApp lifecycle management. Specifically, the defined API exposes endpoints for file management, process execution control, and data logging retrieval. This allows users to upload new xApps as Python scripts to the *xApp executor pod*, check their configuration parameters, run them as independent processes according to their lifetime (i.e., *short-lived* action xApps versus *long-lived* process xApps), monitor their status, and access their execution logs. The API is designed to support asynchronous operations, reliability, and persistence across xApp lifecycles, enabling remote and automated closed-

loop operations, which is particularly convenient for distributed cloud-based orchestration or the integration of AI-driven pipelines without requiring direct shell access to the host running the components.

The required endpoints (i.e., *E2 termination* and *E2 manager* pods, and the designed REST API in the *xApp executor pod*) in the Near-RT RIC blueprint are exposed using the *Load-Balancer* Kubernetes service type. This blueprint is further encapsulated in OSM descriptors (VNF and NS packages), where the flexible templating capabilities of Helm charts are used to generate tailored configuration files for OSM instantiation commands. This enables on-demand, flexible creation of multiple Near-RT RIC instances in the same or different Kubernetes clusters to serve different sets of E2 nodes.

III. DEMONSTRATION

This demonstration showcases the on-demand deployment of a cloud-native instance of the OSC Near-RT RIC and the use of the designed REST API endpoints, which manage the lifecycle of xApps, to interact with and modify the behaviour of a disaggregated cloud-native 5G mobile network featuring multiple slices [4]. The blueprint of the OSC Near-RT RIC is packaged as an NS and can be managed from our MANO stack in the same way as other mobile network components. The main steps of the demonstration are as follows:

- 1) We request our MANO platform to deploy the artefacts corresponding to a two-slice core network (i.e., SST:1 and SST:2). Note that the SMF and UPF functions are disaggregated and distributed across different PoPs, following the deployment described in [4]. Once deployed, the UE information and its slice association are included in the UDR database.
- 2) We proceed with deploying the OSC Near-RT RIC instance at the edge site, where the DU will be located. This placement reduces latency between the xApp and the E2 node.
- 3) The CU and DU components are instantiated in the regional and edge cloud, respectively, after the PTP artefact providing synchronization with the RU is instantiated. These components are configured to serve two slices, as defined in the core network, and an initial Physical Resource Block (PRB) ratio is set for each slice at the DU. When the DU starts, it registers with the running OSC Near-RT RIC instance.

Fig. 2. Modification of PRB allocation ratio of *Slice SST:1* using the proposed remote xApp management API.

4) The UEs are attached to the network. Once flight mode is turned off, each UE receives an IP address within the range of the requested data network (DN). In the core network, one DN is defined and associated with each slice. We start an iperf session from each UE to its assigned UPF to generate downlink traffic.

5) Then, we use the proposed API to list the available xApps and proceed to onboard two xApps developed for this demonstration in the *xApp executor pod*.

6) We launch the developed monitoring xApp (a *long-lived* process) through an available API endpoint. This monitoring xApp interacts with the *E2 Manager* pod to obtain the available E2 nodes and begins listening to the specified KPM *DRB.UEThpDl* metric. By querying another available API endpoint, we can view the reported metrics from a remote computer.

7) While the iperf session and the monitoring xApp are running, we repeatedly invoke the developed Cell Configuration and Control (CCC) xApp to modify the PRB ratio assigned to the selected slice in the DU (*short-lived* process). Each execution of this xApp results in observable variations in the measured throughput of the active iperf session.

During the demonstration, each step is visualized using the MANO platform graphical user interface (GUI), a remote desktop session for smartphone interaction, and command line interface (CLI) windows that show the effects of xApp actions on active iperf sessions through curl requests to the API. Figure 2 shows the reported downlink throughput during a TCP iperf session between the UE attached to *Slice SST:1* and its serving UPF. The observed performance variation corresponds to changes in the PRB ratio, from 25% to 75%, issued through API calls that execute the CCC xApp detailed in Step 7.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This demonstration presented a practical method for automated and portable deployment of the OSC Near-RT RIC. The developed Helm chart, integrated into an ETSI NFV NS package, enables rapid instantiation (less than one minute) and significantly reduces the operational complexity typically associated with Kubernetes-based deployments, without requiring direct access to the target cluster. Additionally, the integrated xApp management API simplifies lifecycle operations, as onboarding and execution of xApps are also performed remotely without cluster access. This approach improves overall computing resource utilization based on xApp lifespan. Together, these capabilities lower the barrier to experimentation with Near-RT RIC functionalities, enabling rapid deployment of closed-loop control prototyping and portable deployment across multiple sites. The framework demonstrated here aims to facilitate future research on intelligent RAN control, thus contributing to the development of the O-RAN ecosystem.

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